

Understanding the historical and future impacts of ENSO on climate and coffee production in Colombia and Indonesia

Passos, E¹, Kaur, L², Sarmiento Herrera, N³

¹ Physical Oceanography Laboratory at the Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro

² SGTB Khalsa College, University of Delhi

³ National Coffee Research Centre - Cenicafé

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10987575

Crop production in Colombia and Indonesia is predominantly carried out by small, family-owned farms, significantly contributing to job creation in rural areas (Purnawan et al., 2021; Sanderson et al., 2022). The El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) influences both countries' rainfall, flooding, drought, and heat waves (Ward et al., 2016; Hao et al., 2018). These ENSO-related weather anomalies substantially affect crop production and farmers' livelihoods (Li et al., 2019; Botero et al., 2022). Coffee production significantly drives the agricultural economies of both nations, being a cornerstone crop with substantial economic impact. Therefore, future droughts and ENSO events may impact coffee production (Almeida et al., 2020). With this in mind, this research aims to explore the diverse impacts of ENSO events on temperature and rainfall patterns, consequently affecting vegetation and coffee production in Colombia and Indonesia.

The Oceanic Niño Index (ONI) (Trenberth et al., 2023) and Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) (Guttman, 1999) were employed to identify ENSO occurrences and regional droughts. The ONI Index was calculated based on the NOAA Optimum Interpolation Sea Surface Temperature for a 3-month rolling mean of the temperature anomaly in the Niño 3.4 region (Banzonet et al., 2016). Based on the historical ONI time series, extreme ENSO events were defined as El Niño above 1.5 and La Niña below -1.5 of the ONI. The SPI was computed using precipitation for 3, 6, 12, and 24-month rolling periods. The 2 m air temperature and precipitation were obtained from the monthly averaged data on single levels of the ERA5 dataset (Hersbach et al., 2020). Besides ONI and SPI, temperature and precipitation distribution were also evaluated for Colombia and Indonesia. The analyzed period spans from 1950 to 2020. In order to explore ENSO's impacts on coffee production in both countries, production statistics from the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) were used between 1995 and 2022. In addition, based on the historical data performance among CMIP6 models, CESM2 results were used to pinpoint potential ENSO events in the SSP2-4.5 scenario.

The results for Indonesia indicate a moderate negative Pearson correlation between ONI and precipitation (-0.4) and temperature (0.5). Meanwhile, in Colombia, the results unveil a robust positive correlation of 0.7 between ONI and temperature and a modest negative correlation of -0.4 between precipitation and ONI. It is crucial to emphasize that all calculated correlations yielded a p-value lower than 0.05, underscoring the statistical significance of this analysis. For Colombia, Poveda et al. (2001) reported that ENSO is the most important interannual phenomenon associated with climatology despite the influence of other occurrences.

Figure 1: Standard Precipitation Index (SPI) for the 12-month rolling period during key climate events - (a) 2015 El Niño in Indonesia, (b) 2015 El Niño in Colombia, (c) 2011 La Niña in Indonesia, (d) 2011 La Niña in Colombia. (e) Time series showing the intensity of ONI and coffee yield anomalies. Additionally, (f) depicts the ONI projections from CESM2 results under the SSP2-4.5 emission scenario. Shaded blue (red) indicates La Niña (El Niño) events below -0.5 (above 0.5), with darker colors indicating extreme events below -1.5 (above 1.5).

In both regions, the SPI exhibited a higher correlation with the 12-month rolling period, and despite being the highest, it remains closely aligned with precipitation values. This heightened correlation value suggests a delayed response, indicating a lagged impact of SPI in this specific time window concerning anomalies in the Niño 3.4 region.

Figures 1a and 1b depict SPI within the 12-month rolling period during the 2015 El Niño event, with red values indicating SPI values below 0. In Indonesia (Figure 1a), nearly the entire geographical expanse experiences drought conditions, except for the western part of Sumatra Island, sections of Borneo, and the eastern region of New Guinea Island, where positive SPI values are observed. The northwest region of Colombia, a crucial area for the country's crop production, exhibits a comparable negative pattern. The pronounced correlation between escalating temperatures and observed drought periods in Indonesia and Colombia (SPI less than -1) is evident, corresponding with positive anomalies in ONI (Figures 1a and 1b).

Figures 1c and 1d showcase SPI during the 2011 La Niña for Indonesia and Colombia. A reversed pattern observed during the El Niño period (Figure 1a) is evident in Indonesia for the La Niña (Figure 1c). Notably, Celebes Island exhibits negative values during La Niña, distinguishing it from El Niño conditions. Conversely, a contrasting pattern emerges in Colombia (Figure 1d), with positive SPI values in the northwest and the southeast approaching zero. During La Niña, both regions experienced rainy periods (SPI above 1), associated with negative anomalies in ONI (Figures 1c and 1d). Consequently, the drought exacerbated by the El Niño events might adversely impact crop production.

The observed pattern suggests a discernible trend, wherein the onset of El Niño conditions is associated with heightened temperatures and diminished precipitation in both regions. This combination adversely influences the SPI, serving as a significant determinant of the conditions experienced by crop fields. The increased temperatures during El Niño contribute to drought-like conditions, intensifying the impact on agriculture.

Conversely, during La Niña events, a contrasting scenario emerges with a negative temperature anomaly. This condition favors a higher likelihood of increased rainfall. The ample precipitation associated with La Niña mitigates the negative effects of drought and provides optimal conditions for robust crop production. It is important to keep in mind that since coffee is a perennial crop, the ENSO condition in a given month impacts production 8 to 9 months later.

Although no clear signal was identified regarding the ENSO events and coffee production in Indonesia, the analysis for Colombia revealed a moderate inverse relationship (Fig. 1 e), indicated by a negative correlation between SPI -12 months and yield anomaly ($r = -0.46$, $p < 0.01$). This result suggests that El Niño has, counterintuitively, been beneficial for coffee production. Previous studies for Colombia support this result (Bastianin et al., 2018; Sanderson et al., 2022) and report that the impact of ENSO phases on coffee production varies depending on the region. Regions with beneficial effects have been those with high rainfall (above 2,000 mm/year) and low sunshine because the increase in temperature that occurs during El Niño, makes flowering more concentrated and often leads to a larger production. In contrast, warm areas, with an average temperature above 21.5°C and low rainfall (below 1,400 mm/year), are more likely to be negatively impacted (Jaramillo & Arcila, 2009). During La Niña, opposite effects occur.

It has been observed that most of the El Niño events exert a significant influence on coffee production in Colombia, whereas in Indonesia, the production of coffee tends to be adversely affected during strong occurrences (Fig. 1 e). Variations in coffee yield may stem from the complexity of Indonesia's rainfall patterns, which are not solely modulated by ENSO but are also influenced by localized factors and the Indian Ocean Dipole (D'Arrigo and Wilson, 2008; Nurdiati et al., 2022). Moreover, strong ENSO events do not show a significant correlation with coffee yield in Indonesia.

Figure 1f showcases the CESM2 ONI projection, emphasizing extreme events associated with El Niño and La Niña (above 1.5 and below -1.5, respectively). In this time series, the initial 25 years notably feature intense La Niña, registering values below -1.5. In contrast, the final three decades exhibit an escalation in the intensity and frequency of extreme El Niño events (above 1.5).

While less intense El Niño typically manifests in the first decades, the CESM2 time series suggests that the occurrence of extreme La Niña events during this period tends to offset drought and diminished crop yields associated with El Niño, thereby enhancing overall agricultural productivity. Nevertheless, a noticeable shift has occurred in the past three decades, marked by an upswing in the intensity and frequency of El Niño projections coupled with a decline in the intensity and frequency of La Niña projections. This change in the pattern projection appears sufficient to face the adverse impacts of El Niño, leading to a decline in coffee production.

The interplay of El Niño and La Niña presents a critical dynamic that directly influences temperature and precipitation patterns, thereby substantially impacting regional crop yields. This work highlights the importance of understanding their temporal distribution for effective agricultural planning and adaptation strategies. Understanding and monitoring these patterns are pivotal for implementing effective agricultural strategies and mitigating the potential consequences of climate variability on crop production.

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